

"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT"

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: "O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI

23-24 OKTYABR

23-24 OCTOBER 2025

2030 UZBEKISTAN STRATEGY

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC TRENDS"

TOSHKENT DAVLAT IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI

FORUM "2030" GLOBAL VA UZBEKISTON - 2030 STRATEGIYA "UZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI

GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: "O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI
GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC TRENDS: "UZBEKISTON-2030" STRATEGY
ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ: СТРАТЕГИЯ «УЗБЕКИСТАН -2030»

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT

2025

ELEKTRON ILMIY JURNAL

MAXSUS SON

- MACROECONOMIC STABILITY
•LABOR MARKET IN THE GREEN ECONOMY
•GLOBAL ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS
•GREEN INVESTMENT AND FINANCING
•GREEN TECHNOLOGIES
•ECO-TOURISM
•GREEN INNOVATIONS

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC TRENDS"

TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

2nd CONFERENCE ON BANKING / FINANCIAL DIRECTION OF THE PRIVATE SECTOR

2030

BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI

**TOSHKENT DAVLAT
IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI**

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: “O‘ZBEKISTON – 2030” STRATEGIYASI FORUMI

(MAXSUS SON)

TOSHKENT–2025

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

ISBN: 978-9910-8110-8-1

UO'K: 004.89(575.1)(062)

KBK: 32.813(5O')ya1

T 97

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayeich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayeich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayeich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

INNOVATSION SIYOSATNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI – OLIY TA'LIM TRANSFORMATSIYASI, RAQAMLI MODERNIZATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH OMILLARI.....	13
Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich	
O'ZBEKISTON YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHI: ZARURAT, MAQSADI VA AYRIM MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLAR	16
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
FAN, TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRISHDAGI SO'NGGI TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSIYALAR	25
To'ychiyev Olimjon Alijonovich	
QURILISH TASHKILOTLARIDA KREDITGA LAYOQATLILIKNI BAHOLASHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH	30
Mavlanov Normo'min Normamatovich	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA DAVLAT XARIDLARINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISHDA ELEKTRON SAVDOLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	37
Turabov Sarvar Abdumalikovich	
O'ZBEKISTONNI MINTAQAVIY TA'LIM VA ILM-FAN HABIGA AYLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	41
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li	
HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYALARIGA INNOVATSION KOMPONENTLARNI INTEGRATSIYA QILISH USULLARI	46
Muminov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li	
OROL DENGIZI MEROSI: EKOLOGIK FOJIANI BARQAROR EKOTURIZM IMKONIYATLARIGA AYLANTIRISH	52
Zufarova Nozima	
KORXONALARNING YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	60
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISHCHI KUCHI BOZORINING TAKRORIY AMAL QILISHINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	66
Mamaraximov B.E.	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR VA MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLARDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI GAROV DIVERSIFIKATSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	70
Xolbozorov Husniddin Norbek o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA MARKETINGNING INNOVATSION KONSEPSIYALARI.....	76
Jumayev Olimjon Sadulloevich, Axmedova Shoxsanam Sindbod qizi	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA EKOLOGIK MAHSULOTLARNI TARG'IB QILISH VA SOTISHNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH USULLARI	84
Jalalova Dildora Jamolovna	
DIRECTIONS OF FORMING AND PROVIDING A COMPETITIVE EXPORT-ORIENTED ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	87
Asatullaev Khurshid Sunatullaevich, Nasirkhodjaeva Dilafruz Sabitkhanovna, Abdullayeva Madina Kamilovna	
FROM SCIENCE TO BUSINESS: HOW UNIVERSITIES STIMULATE INNOVATION	94
Prof. A. Bobozhonov, Prof. A.M. Shatre, Assoc. Prof. V. Kirilova Vladimirova, prof. R.Kh. Karlibaeva	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TECHNOLOGIES IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON ADVANCED INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	100
Otamuratov Sarvar	
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF MIGRATION FROM UZBEKISTAN AND PROSPECTS FOR ORGANIZATIONAL IMPROVEMENT	105
Sabiroya Lola Shavkatovna, Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	

KORXONA BARQAROR AXBOROT TIZIMINI YARATISH QIYINCHILIKLARI.....	112
Abidov Abdujabbar Abduxamidovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATIGA FOIZ RISKINING TA'SIRI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	119
Isakov.J.Ya	
CREATION OF A MECHANISM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND INTRODUCTION OF A MODEL OF COMPLETE TRANSITION TO THE NETZERO ENERGY SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	127
Makhmudova Guljakhon N., Gulomova Nigora Farxadovna	
УСИЛЕНИЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА НА СТОИМОСТНУЮ ОЦЕНКУ ОСНОВНЫХ ФАКТОРОВ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА.....	133
Алишер Расулев, Сергей Воронин	
РОЛЬ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ В РАЗВИТИИ МАЛОГО И СРЕДНЕГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА: ПЕРСПЕКТИВА И ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ ДЛЯ ИХ ПЕРЕХОДА К МСФО.....	143
Эргашева Шахло Тургуновна	
DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMIC ACTIVITY UNDER DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	151
Boburjon Vafoev	
ENERGETIKA TIZIMIDAGI KORXONALAR MOLIYAVIY HOLATINING TAHLILI.....	157
Matnazar Yusupovich Raximov	
АСПЕКТЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЕМ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ.....	162
Очилова Хилола Фармоновна	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLAR.....	167
Abdullayev Suyun Artikovich	
THE INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN DIGITAL LEARNING PLATFORMS AND THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	171
Kuchkarov Takhir Safarovich, Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA BANK FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	174
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich	
РАЗВИТИЕ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА В РАМКАХ ПЕРСПЕКТИВ ВСТУПЛЕНИЯ ВО ВСЕМИРНУЮ ТОРГОВУЮ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЮ	180
У.А.Юлдашева	
ЗЕЛЕННЫЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛИ - ПУТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОГО РОСТА В РАМКАХ УСТОЙЧИВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	185
Дехканова Наргиза Шарифовна	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АУДИТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	192
Ходжаева М.Х.	
TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AHOLINING MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	199
Akbarova Barno Shuxratovna	
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH TOURISM UNDER THE GREEN ECONOMY FRAMEWORK	204
Jumayev Akbar Mahmudovich	
МАКРОИQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BANK TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	210
Erkinxojiyev Ismoiljon Ikromjon o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA MINTAQAVIY SANOAT KORXONALARIDA KORPORATIV MADANIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	216
Matrizayeva Dilaram Yusupbayevna	
UZBEKISTAN AT THE CROSSROADS OF HISTORY AND GREEN INNOVATION: FROM THE GREAT SILK ROAD TO A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE	220
Avalova Gulshod Murodullayevna	

ГЛАВНЫЕ ВЕКТОРЫ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ ПО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	226
Абдуллаева М.К.	
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT IN THE INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN: MODERN TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS.....	233
Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna	
HUDUDDAGI KICHIK BIZNESNING SAMARALI TARKIBIY TUZILMASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MUTASSADI TASHKILOTLARNING O‘ZARO UYG‘UN HARAKATINI TASHKIL ETISH.....	239
Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
BUSINESS ANALYTICS IN HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE: LESSONS FROM THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION TO THE DIGITAL AGE	246
Burxonova Sabo Tulanovna	
“COST ENGINEERING”NING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHDAGI O‘RNI.....	252
Zaynitdinova Umida Djalalovna	
FEATURES AND WAYS OF FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	256
Kobilov Alisher, Majidova Irodahon	
ПИЩЕВАЯ ИНДУСТРИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: АГРАРНЫЙ ИМПУЛЬС, ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ И ЦЕНОВАЯ КОНЪЮНКТУРА.....	263
Юлдашев Голибжон Тургунович, Элдорбеков Гофурбек Искандарбек угли	
INCOME INEQUALITY AND MACROECONOMIC DETERMINANTS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS	273
Muhammad Eid Balbaa, Marina Sagatovna Abdurashidova	
РЫНОК ТРУДА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	276
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи	
EKOLOGIK QO‘RIQXONALARDA MONITORING JARAYONLARINING IQTISODIY VA TASHKILIY ANAMIYATI.....	282
Homidov Hamdam Hasan o‘g‘li	
ГАРМОНИЗАЦИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО	288
Абдужалилова Дилноз Абдусаттаровна	
SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION: CASE OF UZBEKISTAN WITHIN THE UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE FRAMEWORK.....	294
Yuldasheva Dilnoza Ulugbekovna	
ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ НЕЙРОМАРКЕТИНГА НА МАРКЕТПЛЕЙСАХ (WILDBERRIES, UZUM MARKET, ЯНДЕКС МАРКЕТ)	300
Юлдашев Жамшид Абрарович	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК СТИМУЛ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	309
Шаюсупова Наргиза Тургуновна	
GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANISHI O‘ZBEKISTONNING XALQARO SAVDOSIGA VA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TAHDID SIFATIDA.....	315
Mamatov Mamajan Ahmadjonovich	
SUG‘URTA TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH VA INNOVATSION SUG‘URTA MAHSULOTLARINI JORIY QILISH MASALALARI	321
Xalikulova Gulzada Tadjimuratovna	
O‘ZBEKISTON OZIQ-OVQAT BOZORIDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI BARQAROR ISTE‘MOLNI RAG‘BATLANTIRISH	333
Eshmatov Sanjar Azimqulovich	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В РАЗНЫХ ОТРАСЛЯХ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ ОПЫТ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ПРАКТИКА	337
Назарова Ра‘но Рустамовна, Мусаева Гавхар Ахматжон кизи	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA MEHNAT BOZORI: O‘ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	343
Homidjonov Fozilxon Umarxon o‘g‘li, Haydarov Kamoliddin Baratovich	

GREEN INVESTMENT: PATHWAYS TOWARD A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE.....	348
Odilova Sitora Sayfitdin kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	351
Kutbitdinova Mohigul Inoyatovna	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI	356
Metyakubov Azamat Djumanazarovich	
ELEKTR SANOAT KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	361
Tursunxo'jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o'g'li	
УЧЕТ ЗАТРАТ И МЕТОДЫ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ СЕБЕСТОИМОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ	368
Махкамова Саида Гайратовна	
MILLIY HISOBLAR TIZIMIDA INTELLEKTUAL MULK MAHSULOTLARINI MAKROIQTISODIY DARAJADA HISOBGA OLISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSI.....	375
Sunnatov Muxtor Ne'matovich	
RENEWABLE ENERGY AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY IN CENTRAL ASIA: PATHWAYS WITHIN THE GREEN ECONOMY	382
Khabibullo Abdullaev	
JAHON SUG'URTA AMALIYOTI ASOSIDA O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORIDA YANGI RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	387
Abdimovminova Saodat Taxirjonovna	
INTEGRATING DATA SCIENCE INTO GREEN FINANCING AND ECO-INNOVATIONS: ACHIEVING THE GOALS OF UZBEKISTAN-2030	397
Norboev Odil Abraevich, Kungratov Ilmurod Kuzibay ugli	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISHINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASH AMALIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	404
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
СОЗДАНИЕ ЗЕЛЕННОГО ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО КОРИДОРА В ЕВРОПУ: РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА, КАЗАХСТАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	411
Лала Гамидова Адиль, Арзуман Гусейнов Айдын	
MAHALLA TIZIMIDA AHOLINI OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARIGA BO'LGAN ISTE'MOL TALABLARI MODEL.....	419
S. Qulmatova	
AHOLI ICHKI MIGRATSIYASINING MEHNAT BOZORIGA TA'SIRINI STATISTIK O'RGANISH	427
Mirolimov Mirislom Mirshokir o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BANK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH TENDENSIYALARI VA MUAMMOLARI	434
Jumaniyozova Mukaddas Yuldashevna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	438
Фаттахова Муниса	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI SOHASI FAOLIYATINI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH VA BOSHQARISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	444
Tuxtamishev Shodimurod Qurbonboyevich	
MARKETING TADQIQOTLARI ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOT MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORT SALONIYATINI OSHIRISH	452
Xojiyev Elshod Yoqub o'g'li	
СПОСОБЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НАУЧНЫМИ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯМИ В ЦЕЛЯХ ПЕРЕХОДА НА РАЗРАБОТКУ ЗЕЛЕННЫХ ИННОВАЦИЙ	459
Юдаков Александр Андреевич	
O'ZBEKISTONNI JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA A'ZO BO'LISHINING OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHGA TA'SIRI.....	466
Axmedova N.A.	

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KLASTERLAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI	471
<i>Sherkulov Shohruh Erkin o'g'li</i>	
DEVELOPMENT SCENARIOS OF UZBEKISTAN'S ACTIVE LABOR FORCE UNTIL 2030 AND THEIR ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS.....	476
<i>Ganiev Bakhtiyor Zulfikor ugli, Rakhmonov Bekzod Sharibjon ugli</i>	
РАЗВИТИЕ ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ КАК ФАКТОР СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ ЖЕНЩИН В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	481
<i>Дониерова Фотимабону Алишер кизи</i>	
YASHIL ENERGETIKA VA UNING IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTDAGI O'RNI	488
<i>Babadjanova Malika Ruzimova</i>	
BENCHMARKING IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY: STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVENESS	492
<i>Abdurashidova Nigora</i>	
УЗБЕКИСТАН СТРЕМИТСЯ К УСТОЙЧИВОМУ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМУ РОСТУ, ВНЕДРЯЯ ПРИНЦИПЫ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ	498
<i>Сагдуллаева Гулнора Ботыровна</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KOMPANIYALARNING GLOBAL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	502
<i>Sharipov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich</i>	
ZAIF BANDLIKDAN UNUMLI BANDLIK SARI TRANSFORMATSIYA: O'ZINI O'ZI BAND QILISH	507
<i>Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich</i>	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМАЯ ЭНЕРГИЯ В ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ТЕКУЩИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И БУДУЩЕЕ РАЗВИТИЕ.....	514
<i>Меҳрибан Самедова Тофик</i>	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISHGA TA'SIRI	521
<i>Zafar Alisherovich Mamadiev, Nodira Isametdinovna Xasanxonova</i>	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA INTEGRATSIYA QILISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	526
<i>Ablazov Lazizbek Abdiquosimovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING TRANSFORMATSIYASI JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	530
<i>Ziyadullaev Z.</i>	
TO'LOV TIZIMI KONSEPTUAL MODELINING SHAKLLANISH TAMOYILLARI	537
<i>Toshniyozov Sherali Kamoliddinovich</i>	
STAFF PERFORMANCE EVALUATION BASED ON KPI SYSTEM INDICATORS.....	546
<i>Rakhmatullaeva Shakhnoza Khamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchkhon</i>	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC TRENDS	555
<i>Svetlana Yurievna Shatokhina</i>	
MILLIY TARBIYA OMILLARI VA MILLIY MADANIY YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TALABALARDA O'QUV TASHABBUSKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-AMALIY ASOSLARI.....	560
<i>Azimova Nilufar Nuriddinovna</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINI TA'MINLASHDA BANK RESURSLARINING ROLI	567
<i>Xodjayeva Jeyrona Ravshonbek qizi</i>	
O'QUV DASTURINI INTEGRATSIYALASH VA YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: AKADEMIK VA SANOAT O'RTASIDAGI TAFOVUTNI YOPISSH	572
<i>Qo'ziqulova Dilfuzaxon Maxammatisaqovna</i>	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND DIGITAL PLATFORMS AS A KEY FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES	580
<i>Rizayeva Nilufar Oblakulovna</i>	

IQTISODIY OLIY TA'LIMDA STRATEGIK INNOVATSIYALAR: YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI MILLIY VA GLOBAL BARQARORLIK MAQSADLARI BILAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH	585
<i>Xasanova Zarina Maxamadaliyeva</i>	
MARKAZIY OSIYODA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH YO'LIDAGI TO'SIQLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	594
<i>Aminov Shovkat O'ktam o'g'li</i>	
ПЕСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	598
<i>Саидахмедова Аида Мирзаевна</i>	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И СНИЖЕНИЕ РИСКОВ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ТРАНЗАКЦИЙ В ФИНАНСОВЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ СИСТЕМАХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СИММЕТРИЧНЫХ КРИПТОСИСТЕМ.....	605
<i>Раҳимбердиев Қ.Б.</i>	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ И СТРАХОВЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ДЛЯ СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА	612
<i>Ш.Ф.Кобилжонова</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ КАПИТАЛА ХОЗЯЙСТВУЮЩИХ СУБЪЕКТОВ В КОНТЕКСТЕ РАЗВИТИЯ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА ЭКОНОМИКИ	618
<i>Д.А.Юлдашева</i>	
РОЛЬ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И СТРАХОВЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В СТИМУЛИРОВАНИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА	624
<i>Г.Т.Ахмедова</i>	
SUG'URTA BOZORI FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TRANSFORMATSIYALASH VA UNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	630
<i>Saidov Farrux Faxriddinovich</i>	
OPPORTUNITIES TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE ENERGY SECTOR THROUGH THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY.....	635
<i>Ulashov Aliboy Rashid ugli, Istamova Nasiba Narzillo kizi</i>	
INKLYUZIV OLIY TA'LIMDA MUSTAQIL ISHLASH JARAYONINI TASHKILLASHTIRISH.....	641
<i>Akbarova Kamola Abdujabbor qizi</i>	
YOUTH-DRIVEN PATHWAYS TO GREEN EMPLOYMENT: A THEORETICAL EXAMINATION OF INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC STRATEGIES	646
<i>Suvpulatov Ozodjon Alijon ugli</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR VA UNING O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN AHAMIYATI	651
<i>Botirova Xulkar Olimjonovna</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH KLASTERLARI: NAZARIY ASOSLAR VA AMALIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	655
<i>Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi</i>	
BIOTECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS IN URBAN PLANNING: OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS OF "LIQUID TREES"	660
<i>Nosirkulov Asadjon Ahmadjon ugli</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARINING O'RNI.....	663
<i>Fayziyeva Dilso'z Bahodirovna</i>	
KREDIT PORTFELIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLAR ULUSHINI KAMAYTIRISH YO'LLARI	668
<i>Salixova G.J</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	672
<i>Boboyorova Maftuna Xaqqul qizi, Boboyorov Islombek Xaqqul o'g'li</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH METODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	675
<i>Xusniddinov Yorqinjon Muhiddin o'g'li</i>	

MODA SANOATIDA CRM TIZIMLARINI ELEKTRON SAVDO PLATFORMALARI BILAN UYG'UNLASHTIRISHDAGI TO'SIQLAR	679
Xalilova Nafisa Komilovna	
ENHANCING FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS AS A DRIVING FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY	683
Khaitova Feruza Bahrom kizi	
MARKAZIY OSIYO MAMLAKATLARIDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARIGA TA'SIRI	687
Akishova Shaxnoza Davlet qizi	
BUXORO VILOYATIDA HUNARMANDCHILIK FAOLIYATINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	693
Ravshanova Gulchexra Ravshanovna	
SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MEKANIZMLARI TURLARI VA OLIMLARNING YONDASHUVLARI	698
Ne'matov Shoxruxbek Ma'murjon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA UNING XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI.....	703
Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA REAL SEKTORNI KREDITLASH MEKANIZMLARINI SAMARALI JORIY ETISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJIGA TA'SIRI.....	709
Abduxomidov Ikromjon Maxamadin o'g'li	
MOLIYA TIZIMIDA BOJ-TARIF SIYOSATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI (OZIQ-OVQAT IMPORTI MISOLIDA).....	715
Rizaev Mirmahmud Xotamjanovich	
YASHIL MARKETING VA ESG INTEGRATSIYASI: STATISTIK TAHLIL VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	721
Charos G'ayratova	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО КАПИТАЛА ДЛЯ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	727
Г.А.Хайитбаева	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLAR TOMONIDAN TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI KREDITLASH.....	734
Tajiddinov Jamshiddin Shamsutdinovich	
IQTISODIYOTNING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASIGA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALAR TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	738
Shodiboyeva Dilzoda Farhodjon qizi	
MOLIYA TIZIMI BARQARORLIGI VA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING AHAMIYATI.....	743
Aktamov Akbarjon Aslan o'g'li	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CARBON EMISSIONS AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.....	748
Shakhriddinova Sitara Tolibjon kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH JARAYONIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA ESG TAMOYILLARINING ROLI	760
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA SANOAT KORXONALARIDA YETKAZIB BERISH STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	769
Yusupov Ulug'bek Mamayusupovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONTEKSTIDA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASH: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI.....	776
Isroilov Islomiddin Kamoliddin o'g'li	

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SPORT TASHKILOTLARINING YANGI BIZNES MODELLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	782
G'ulomov Musirmon	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTISIYALARNI JALB ETISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	786
Sharipova Shahnoza Baxtiyorovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTISIYA MUHITIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA INVESTISIYALARNING IQTISODIYOTGA JALB ETILISH HOLATI TAHLILI	795
Karimova Qunduz Atanazarovna	
O'ZBEKISTON TURISTIK XIZMATLAR BOZORIDA BANDLIK TRANSFORMATSIYASINI VA UNI TARTIBGA SOLISH HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH	804
To'xtayeva Xurshida Farxodovna	
INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI INVESTITSIYA RISKLARINI BAHOLASH.....	811
Zohidova Ruksora Komiljon qizi	
ТИПЫ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РАЗВЕДОК: ОСНОВНЫЕ РАЗЛИЧИЯ, ФОРМЫ И МЕТОДЫ ОСУЩЕСТВЛЕНИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	817
Эсанов Шохрух Отабекович	
FACE RECOGNITION PROGRAM IN PYTHON.....	823
Khurramova Maftunakhon Zhurabekovna, Khurramov Azizjon Bakhodir ugli	
FORMATION OF ACCOUNTING POLICY FOR INTANGIBLE ASSETS.....	827
Farxod T. Abdvaxidov, Ramazon A. Abdurakhmanov	
O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORT TARKIBINI YUQORI QO'SHIMCHA QIYMATLI MAHSULOTLARGA O'TKAZISH STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	834
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
EKSPORT FAOLIYATIDA ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	838
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
TURIZM KLASTERLARIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLAR INTEGRATSIYASI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	841
Yazdanova Shohista Tuyg'un qizi Farxodova Shohnoza Umidbek qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON HAVO TRANSPORTI TIZIMINING JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	850
Azimova Moxinur Nozimovna	

DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMIC ACTIVITY UNDER DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Boburjon Vafoev

Tashkent State University of Economics,
Professor of the Department of "Digital Economy",
Candidate of Economic Sciences
Email: boburvafo@gmail.com

Abstract: This scientific article, prepared as part of a dissertation study, is devoted to the analysis of the digital transformation of economic activity in agriculture. The research is based on the review of scientific works, statistical data, regulatory legal frameworks, and the results of the author's survey conducted among peasant (farm) households and rural individual entrepreneurs. Particular attention is paid to the systematization of factors that determine the specifics of launching the digital transformation process in agriculture, including information provision, infrastructural aspects, the level of digital maturity of producers, and the development of the industry's innovation system. The analysis of modern studies shows that the use of IT solutions in the production process has significant advantages compared to traditional farming: it increases labor productivity, reduces production costs, and enhances competitiveness. However, insufficient expertise in IT applications, limited financial opportunities, and lack of qualified personnel remain the main obstacles to digital development in agriculture. The article also reveals the dependence of the speed of introducing IT solutions on production volumes and highlights the link between digitalization and the effective development of agribusiness. Four levels of digitalization are identified: digital governance, digital economy, data-driven economy, and digital communication.

Key words: digital transformation, digital technologies, IT solutions, infrastructural features, agriculture.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur ilmiy maqola dissertatsiya ishining bir qismi sifatida tayyorlangan bo'lib, qishloq xo'jaligida iqtisodiy faoliyatning raqamli transformatsiyasi xususiyatlarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqot olimlarning ilmiy ishlari, statistik ma'lumotlar, normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar, shuningdek, muallif tomonidan dehqon (fermer) xo'jaliklari va qishloqdagi yakka tartibdagi tadbirkorlar o'rtasida o'tkazilgan so'rov natijalari asosida olib borilgan. Ayniqsa, raqamli transformatsiya jarayonini boshlashga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni tizimlashtirishga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Bular qatoriga tarmoqni ma'lumot bilan ta'minlash, infratuzilmaviy jihatlari, ishlab chiqaruvchilarning raqamli yetuklik darajasi hamda soha innovatsion tizimining rivojlanishi kiradi. Tahlil natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, ishlab chiqarish jarayonida axborot texnologiyalari yechimlaridan foydalanish an'anaviy usullarga nisbatan ko'plab afzalliklarga ega: mehnat unumdorligini oshiradi, ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarini kamaytiradi va raqobatbardoshlikni kuchaytiradi. Shu bilan birga, malakali kadrlarning yetishmasligi, moliyaviy imkoniyatlarning cheklanganligi va axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish bo'yicha bilim darajasining pastligi sohaning raqamli rivojlanishidagi asosiy to'siqlar sifatida qayd etilgan. Maqolada axborot texnologiyalari yechimlarini joriy etish sur'ati xo'jalik sub'yektlarining ishlab chiqarish hajmiga bog'liqligi, shuningdek, raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish bilan qishloq xo'jaligi biznesining samarali rivojlanishi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik ochib beriladi. Raqamlashtirish darajalari to'rtta yo'nalishda belgilangan: raqamli boshqaruv, raqamli iqtisodiyot, ma'lumotga asoslangan iqtisodiyot va raqamli kommunikatsiya.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli transformatsiya, raqamli texnologiyalar, axborot texnologiyalari yechimlari, infratuzilmaviy xususiyatlar, qishloq xo'jaligi.

Аннотация: Данная научная статья подготовлена в рамках диссертационного исследования и посвящена изучению особенностей цифровой трансформации экономической деятельности в сельском хозяйстве. Исследование основано на анализе научных трудов ученых, статистических данных, нормативно-правовой базы, а также данных, полученных в результате авторского опроса среди представителей крестьянских (фермерских) хозяйств и сельских индивидуальных предпринимателей. Особое внимание уделено систематизации факторов, определяющих специфику начала процесса цифровой трансформации аграрного сектора: обеспечение информацией, инфраструктурные аспекты, уровень цифровой зрелости производителей и развитие инновационной системы отрасли. Анализ современных исследований показал, что использование ИТ-решений в производственном процессе имеет значительные преимущества по сравнению с традиционным земледелием: рост производительности труда, снижение издержек и повышение конкурентоспособности. Вместе с тем низкий уровень знаний специалистов в области применения ИТ, ограниченные финансовые ресурсы и дефицит кадров остаются ключевыми барьерами цифрового развития сельского хозяйства. В статье также показана зависимость темпов внедрения цифровых технологий от объемов производства аграрных субъектов и раскрыта взаимосвязь между цифровизацией и эффективным развитием агробизнеса. Определены четыре уровня цифровизации: цифровое управление, цифровая экономика, экономика, основанная на данных, и цифровая коммуникация.

Ключевые слова: цифровая трансформация, цифровые технологии, ИТ-решения, инфраструктурные особенности, сельское хозяйство.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the process of digital transformation is large-scale and affects most sectors of economic activity, including the agricultural sector, which plays an important role in ensuring the country's food security. With the increase in population and its density, society's need for food products is increasing year by year, but the available resources remain finite and limited. This problem reveals the need to develop a new approach to the process of modernization of the agricultural industry, to establish an effective work mechanism taking into account the use of digital technological solutions.

The urgency of the process of digital transformation of economic activity in agriculture is related to increasing the efficiency of the production process. Due to the introduction of specialized «smart» equipment for production, the use of artificial intelligence technologies, digital detailing of statistical data, as well as the use of digital platform solutions and network databases, production losses are reduced, labor productivity is increased. increased, product quality improved.

The object of research is the process of digital transformation of agriculture.

The subject of research is information technology solutions used in the production process of certain categories of agriculture.

to analyze the results expected from the digital transformation of some categories of agriculture during the introduction and use of information technology solutions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is based on the analysis of available statistical data, literature sources, as well as the latest articles in the field of IT.

To achieve the goal of the research, the following tasks were set:

- to study the characteristics of the process of digital transformation of economic activity and to determine the characteristic consequences of the introduction of digital technologies into the production process;
- to identify the main obstacles preventing the use of information technology solutions in the agricultural sector;
- to determine the rate of introduction of information technology solutions to different categories of agricultural producers depending on their production volume;
- description of the importance of infrastructural features in the framework of digital transformation of economic activity on the example of peasant farms and rural individual entrepreneurs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on the digital transformation process can be divided into several areas, based on customer experience, operational processes and business models. As a rule, the study of the digital transformation process is based on these components and Kravchenko N.A. [1], Gribanova Yu.I. [2], Tolstykh T.O. [3], Tsenjarik M.K. [4], Ermolenko O.D. [5] reflected in the research. It should be noted that the topic of digital transformation of agriculture and the formation of a mechanism for the introduction of information and technological solutions

into the field occupies a wide place among modern researches. However, there are very few studies devoted to the infrastructural aspects of the activities of small-scale agriculture and the prospects of digital transformation of small-scale agriculture, so this research can be considered relevant and has scientific novelty.

The research is based on theoretical and methodological principles developed by local scientists.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In writing the scientific publication, the author used the following methods: analysis and synthesis of scientific studies and articles, regulatory documents and documents, analysis of statistical data, as well as tabular and graphic methods of visualizing statistical data.

The process of digital transformation represents the transition to conducting business based on a comprehensive change of the company's operations, business processes and business models, maximizing the capabilities of digital technologies. Digital transformation often leads to the emergence of new businesses, customers and markets. In order to remain competitive, enterprises must take a strategic approach to assessing digital opportunities and understand internal and external environmental factors. It is also worth noting that the main factors of the digital transformation process include mobility (access to the Internet), the constant increase in the volume of data, computerization, the spread of network technologies, and the speed of economic processes. development of digital technologies, including artificial intelligence, formation of an ecosystem for integrated implementation of innovative processes and use of digital solutions [6].

It should be noted that various studies on the introduction of digital technological solutions in agriculture are directly related to the processes of automation of production, forecasting of current yields, estimation of the cost of existing products and profit calculations [7]. At present, there are various categories for the dissemination of technologies for the digital transformation of economic activity in agriculture. Digital transformation technologies can be based on the management system of agricultural enterprises: precision agriculture and animal husbandry, digital service of agrometeorological data, monitoring of agricultural equipment, drones, Big Data, robotics, markets, biotechnology and genetic engineering, alternative forms [8]. Other authors suggest dividing digital technologies into the main groups of «smart» agricultural technologies, including «precision agriculture», «agricultural robots», «AIoT platforms / AIoT applications», «Big data» [9]. Digital transformation of economic activity will help increase the competitiveness of the agricultural industry, attract investments, reduce the cost of agricultural products, as well as provide reliable and timely information about the current state of this industry and related industries. allows to obtain [10].

In the author's research, digital technologies are divided into four categories of information technology solutions: agricultural accounting and planning technologies (for example, 1C program: Accounting for an agricultural enterprise, 1C: Document circulation, etc.), automation technologies units (e.g. digital sensors, measurement transducers, position sensors, pressure velocity, force, etc.), forecasting technologies (e.g., remote sensing technologies, crop yield forecasting technologies, analytical software, etc.), information collection and transmission technologies (mobile terminals, communication system with a mobile video surveillance station, unmanned aerial vehicles, etc.) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Application of different types of information technology solutions by peasant (farm) farms and rural individual entrepreneurs (compiled by the author)

According to the received data, agricultural activity accounting and planning technologies are currently used most (65%) by peasant (farmer) enterprises and rural individual entrepreneurs, in second place are division automation technologies (55%), followed by information collection and transmission technologies (40%), forecasting technologies (37%). Taking into account the use of information technology solutions in their activities, it should be noted that the representatives of peasant farms and rural individual entrepreneurs are highly interested and open to the process of introducing digital mechanisms into their production activities.

At the same time, there are a number of factors that prevent the introduction of information technology solutions in agriculture (Table 1). The main factor is the insufficient knowledge of the representatives of peasant (farm) households and rural individual entrepreneurs on the practical application of digital transformation and information technology solutions. It should also be noted that small and medium-sized businesses, due to the fragmentation of the information infrastructure, often turn to the help of specialized consulting centers using the principle of outsourcing. This problem shows the need to improve the means of digital transformation of economic activity in agriculture, which can be expressed in the formation of network databases and expert communities.

Table 1. Factors preventing the implementation of information technology solutions in agriculture

Factors preventing the introduction of information technology solutions in agriculture	Interest distribution
Lack of readiness of agricultural business for digital innovations	24.7 %
Lack of sufficient knowledge in the field of digitization	55.8 %
Lack of financial opportunities in the implementation of digital technologies in production	51.9 %
There is not enough support from the state in the digitalization of agricultural business	35.1 %
Reluctance to change the traditional way of business management to new ways of management	36.4 %
Lack of specialized personnel, insufficient qualification of experts in the field of digital technologies	46.8 %
There is no clear need to introduce digital methods in agricultural business management	19.5 %
The complexity of the process of introducing digital solutions, the lack of guarantees of their high efficiency	29.8 %

The second obstacle is the lack of financial opportunities to introduce digital technological solutions into the production process. The third reason that prevents the implementation of information technology solutions in agriculture is the lack of personnel and the insufficient level of skills of specialists in the field of digital technologies. This problem is the lack of knowledge, skills and qualifications for the use of digital technological solutions in the production, not having the necessary, correct and timely information, one of the main problems in the process of managing the enterprise. once again confirms that.

To a lesser extent, factors related to the reluctance of industry representatives to change the traditional way of business management to new management methods, issues of government support for agribusiness, the labor-intensive process of implementing digital solutions and the lack of readiness of agribusiness are implications for digital innovation. Despite the fact that the digital transformation of small and medium-sized agricultural enterprises is scattered compared to large-scale agricultural enterprises, the majority of respondents from farmers and rural entrepreneurs see the need to introduce digital methods. In agricultural business management, the factor «lack of visible need to introduce digital methods in agricultural business management» has taken an extreme place among other factors that prevent the introduction of information technology solutions in the agricultural sector.

To determine the rate of implementation of information technology solutions for different categories of agricultural producers (households, peasant farms, medium-sized agricultural enterprises, large agricultural farms) It is recommended to apply to the National Research Institute. According to the results of this study, the level of demand among agricultural producers for the use of digital technological solutions in their activities directly affects the need to form an agricultural production information system. is showing a secret. The level of demand for new technological solutions among different categories of agriculture (households, peasant farms, medium-sized agricultural enterprises) can be observed as follows (Table 2):

Implementation potential for farms: high (organic agriculture, waste-free (circular) agriculture), medium

(drip irrigation, integrated pest management), low (precision agriculture, large conveyor livestock, urbanized agriculture, automation and computerization, biofuels).

Potential for adoption by households: high (zero-waste (circular) agriculture), medium (organic agriculture, integrated pest management), low (precision agriculture, large-scale conveyor livestock, drip irrigation, urbanized agriculture, automation and computerization, biofuels).

Adoption potential of agricultural products: high (integrated pest management, biofuels), medium (organic agriculture, precision agriculture, drip irrigation, automation and computerization, rotational agriculture 'jaligi'), low (large-scale conveyor farming, urbanized agriculture).

Large agricultural holdings have a high potential for introducing new technologies according to almost all indicators of technological solutions, except for waste-free (circular) agriculture (average implementation potential) and organic agriculture economy (low implementation potential) is excluded.

Data analysis shows the uneven distribution of the digital development of certain categories of agriculture, which is explained by the level of profitability, the scale of production, the specialization of production, as well as the dispersion of organizational units of business entities. The study of the potential of the introduction of technology describes the ability of agricultural enterprises to use a digital business model based on the automation of the entire cycle of the production chain for comprehensive digitization of production, automation of the maximum number of economic activity processes. In turn, the potential for introducing new technological solutions to small and medium-sized agricultural enterprises is scattered, which indicates the possibility of introducing information technology solutions only through the automation of individual management functions. Such functions include accounting, food market monitoring and business planning [11].

Table 2. Demand for new technologies by economic entities of the agro-industrial complex

Technology	Personal auxiliary farms (subsidiary farming)	Farms/individual entrepreneurs (semi-commodity farm)	Medium-sized agricultural enterprises, social entrepreneurship corporation (commodity)	Large agricultural holdings (commodity, export-oriented farming)
Organic farming	M	H	M	L
Precision agriculture	L	L	M	H
Large conveyor belt farming	L	L	L	H
Drip irrigation	L	M	M	H
Integrated pest management	M	M	H	H
Urbanized agriculture	L	L	L	H
Automation and computerization	L	L	M	H
Zero-waste (circular) agriculture	H	H	M	M
Biofuel	L	L	H	H

Technology implementation potential: H - high, M - medium, L - low.

In general, the low potential of introducing digital technologies in smallest and medium forms of agriculture is a serious obstacle to the digital transformation of the sector's economic activity. In this regard, the agricultural industry faces the task of forming a comprehensive approach to the process of introducing digital technologies, as well as supporting agro-startups, which are the vector of development of this sector [12].

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Thus, the mechanism of agricultural management is experiencing a number of important changes due to the large-scale digital transformation of economic activity, the state, realizing the need to introduce digital

technologies into the agricultural industry, is rapidly modernizing the management business model. using digital components. Digital management of agriculture involves monitoring the quality and quantity of the produced products, analyzing the efficiency and effectiveness of enterprise activities, collecting and processing large amounts of data in order to create a single statistical database. The study of new trends in agricultural management serves the development of the agricultural sector, the effective use of the resource potential of our country with the correct distribution of costs, and the preparation of a pool of personnel with digital skills. The basis of strategic planning for the development of the agricultural industry is scientific and technical forecasting, taking into account global, social, ecological and technological problems.

The study of the possibilities of introducing digital technologies into the economic activities of agricultural producers showed that the speed of introducing digital technological solutions is directly related to the production volume of economic entities. The rate of adoption of digital technologies in large agricultural enterprises is significantly higher than that of medium and small enterprises, which is due to the differentiated level of financial capabilities, production scale, related to the release concentration level. However, due to the increasing trend of widespread distribution and use of digital technology solutions, the availability of digital technologies is increasing, the user mechanism is being simplified, the cost of digital technologies is decreasing, which will lead to an increase in the number of digital technologies over time.

The article lists the main obstacles that prevent the introduction of digital technologies in the agricultural sector: lack of sufficient knowledge in the field of digitization, lack of financial opportunities to introduce digital technological solutions into the production process, lack of qualified specialists. employees. As a solution to these problems, it is appropriate to consider the possibilities of improving the means of digital transformation of economic activity, expressed in the formation of network databases and expert communities, which provide a quick solution to problems in the field of agriculture.

The data of the author's research showed that digital technological solutions are already finding their piecemeal application in the economic activities of small forms of agriculture, the introduction of digital technologies and the effective development of agricultural business at four levels of digitization the relationship between Agricultural accounting and planning technologies are the most common, unit automation technologies are also used, information collection and transmission technologies and forecasting technologies are used less often. In order to accelerate the process of introduction and application of digital technological solutions in agriculture, it is necessary to ensure effective cooperation between the subjects of separate agricultural sectors, to modernize the infrastructural features of activities that allow to ensure the continuity of reproduction processes.

List of used literature

1. Digital transformation and problems of high-tech business / N.A. Kravchenko, V.D. Markova, N.P. Baldin and others / ed. Dan. OVER. Kravchenko, Doctor of Economics VD Markova. – Novosibirsk: IEOPP SB RAS, 2019. - 352 p.
2. Gribanov Yu.I. Digital transformation of business: textbook / Yu.I. Gribanov, MN Rudenko. - 2nd edition. - Moscow: Dashkov and K, 2021. - 213 p.
3. Tolstix T.O. A set of tools for managing business projects of innovative enterprises in the digital economy / T.O. Tolstix, V.A. Khvostikova; International Academy of Science and Practice of Production Organization, Voronezh State Technical University. - Voronezh: Voronezh State. Technical University, 2016. - 237 p.
4. Tsenjarik M.K., Krylova Yu.V., Steshenko V.I. Digital transformation of companies: strategic analysis, influencing factors and models. Newsletter of St. Petersburg University. Economy. 2020. – T. 36. Number 3. – P. 390-420.
5. Ermolenko O.D. Problems and prospects of the development of Russian agriculture in the conditions of digital transformation and the role of human capital // Reclamation as a driver of modernization of the agro-industrial complex in the conditions of climate change. 2020. – p. 206-211.
6. Kochetkov E.P. Digital transformation of the economy and technological revolutions: problems for the current paradigm of management and crisis management // Strategic decisions and risk management. 2019. - T. 10. No. 4. - p. 330-341.
7. Buklagin D.S. Digital technologies for agricultural management // International journal of scientific research. 2021. No. 2-1(104). – P. 136-144.
8. Dobrovlyanin V.D., Antineskul E.A. Digitization of agriculture: the current level of digitization in the Russian Federation and prospects for further development // Digital models and solutions. 2022. T. 1, No. 2, p. 5.
9. Sibiryayev A.S., Zazimko V.L., Dodov R.X. Digital transformation and digital platforms in agriculture // Bulletin of NGIEI. 2020 year. 12 (No. 115). Pages 96–108.
10. Oborin MS Digital innovative technologies in agriculture // Urals agrarian bulletin. 2022. 5 (No. 220). – P. 82-92.
11. Usenko L.N., Kholodov O.A. Digital transformation of agriculture // Accounting and statistics. 2019 year. No. 1(53). p. 87-102.
12. Vartanova M.L. Prospects of digitalization of agriculture as a priority for import substitution / M.L. Vartanova, E.V. Drobot // Economic relations. 2018 – Volume 8. – No. 1. – P. 1-18.
13. Departmental project «Digital agriculture»: official publication. - M.: FGBNU «Rosinformagrotech», 2019. - 48 p.

**TOSHKENT DAVLAT
IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI**

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: “O‘ZBEKISTON – 2030” STRATEGIYASI FORUMI

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT

Ilmiy elektron jurnal

(MAXSUS SON)

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o‘g‘li

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug‘bek tumani
Kumushkon ko‘chasi, 26-uy.

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS
AND MATHEMATICS

23-24

OCTOBER
2030

23-24
OCTOBER
2025

1st CONFERENCE:
DIRECTIONS FOR ENSURING
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC
GROWTH IN THE CONTEXT OF
TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY

3RD CONFERENCE:
MACHINE LEARNING AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE:
A NEW APPROACH TO ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL
AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS"

UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY
23-24 OCTOBER

- ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES
- ECONOMETRICS AND
BUSINESS ANALYTICS
- DATA SCIENCE (DATABASES)
- DIGITAL GOVERNMENT
- DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION
- ECONOMIC STATISTICS
- QUANTITATIVE MEASUREMENT
OF THE ECONOMY

2nd CONFERENCE:
BANKING AND
FINANCIAL SYSTEM AND
DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING
THE PRIVATE SECTOR

23-24 2025
OCTOBER

- Makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik
- Yashil iqtisodiyotda
mehnat bozori
- Jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro
iqtisodiy munosabatlar
- Yashil investitsiya va kreditlash
- Yashil texnologiyalar
- Eko turizm
- Yashil innovatsiyalar

СТРАТЕГИЯ
«УЗБЕКИСТАН –2030»

23-24 2025
OCTOBER

- Makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik
- Yashil iqtisodiyotda
mehnat bozori
- Jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro
iqtisodiy munosabatlar
- Yashil investitsiya va kreditlash
- Yashil texnologiyalar
- Eko turizm
- Yashil innovatsiyalar

strategy2025.tsue.uz

YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH
SHAROITIDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY
O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH YO'NALISHLARI

2030

<https://strategy2025.tsue.uz/>

TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS
ФОРУМ UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY

ISSN: 2992-8982

Elektron pochta: sq1141983@gmail.com

Telefon: +998 93 124 57 11

Sayt: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Telegram: https://t.me/taraqqiyot_va_talim_uz

ISBN 978-9910-8110-8-1

9 789910 811081

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL
AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS"

1st CONFERENCE:
DIRECTIONS FOR ENSURING
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC
GROWTH IN THE CONTEXT OF
TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY

2030
UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY

BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI
VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI
RIVOJLANTIRISH
YO'NALISHLARI